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Research Article

**Severe Malaria in Children in Mauritania: A Five-Year Retrospective Study at the
Mother-Child Hospital Center of Nouakchott**

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Abstract**Introduction**

Malaria is a potentially fatal parasitic infectious disease that poses a major public health problem. Our objective was to study the epidemiological, clinical, paraclinical, therapeutic, and evolutionary profile of severe malaria in children in Mauritania.

Patients and methods

Retrospective study of the records of children hospitalized in the pediatric department of the Mother-Child Hospital Center of Nouakchott from January 1, 2015 to December 31, 2016.

Results

Males were predominant (55%) (sex ratio = 1.2). The most affected age group was 1 month to 5 years (58%), with a peak in admissions in October.

Fever was the most frequent reason for hospitalization (62.74%). Prostration was the most frequently observed criterion of severity (56%).

Severe anemia was present in 17% of cases, and thrombocytopenia was observed in two-thirds of cases.

The outcome was favorable in 98% of cases.

Conclusion: *Severe malaria manifests itself in several clinical forms depending on the transmission area.*

Keywords: *Severe malaria – Plasmodium falciparum – child – Nouakchott*

Introduction

Malaria remains a major public health problem in sub-Saharan Africa [1]. In Mauritania, despite progress in prevention, severe forms persist, particularly among children [2–4].

According to the WHO, severe malaria is defined as a life-threatening parasitic infection in the absence of any other obvious cause. Few national studies have explored its clinical and evolutionary characteristics in children in Mauritania.

The objective was to describe the epidemiological, clinical, paraclinical, therapeutic and evolutionary profile of children hospitalized for severe malaria at the CHME in Nouakchott.

Methodology

Type of study

Retrospective descriptive study conducted from January 1, 2015 to December 31, 2016.

Study population

Children aged 1 month to 16 years hospitalized for severe malaria in the general pediatrics department of CHME.

Inclusion criteria

- Rapid diagnostic test (RDT) or positive blood smear
- Presence of at least one WHO severity criterion

Exclusion criteria

- Incomplete or unused files

Data collected

Age, sex, medical history, clinical signs, laboratory results, treatment administered, evolution. Statistical analysis performed using Excel and SPSS 20.

Results

Epidemiology

- Total hospitalizations: 4,280
- Cases of severe malaria: 51 (1.19%)
- Average age: 4.8 years
- Children under 5 years old: 58%
- Sex ratio: 1.2 (predominantly males)
- Seasonal peak: October

Clinical and biological aspects

- Fever: 62.7%
- Prostration: 56%
- Altered consciousness: 92%
- Anemia: 57%
- Jaundice: 17.6%
- Respiratory distress: 9.8%
- Thrombocytopenia: 66% (of which 27% < 50,000/mm³)
- Positive TDR: 98%
- Positive smear: 1.97%

Treatment

- Quinine IV: 50 patients
- IV artesunate: 1 patient
- Antibiotic therapy: 100%
- Transfusions: 15 patients

Evolution

- Favorable: 98%
- Death: 1 patient (1.97%)
- Average length of hospital stay: 4.6 days (3 to 21 days)

Discussion

The observed male predominance is consistent with studies conducted in Senegal, Congo-Brazzaville, Mali, Nigeria and Mauritania [5–9].

The majority of cases involve children under 5 years old, consistent with African literature [7–13].

Fever remains the primary reason for hospitalization, as observed in Senegal [14], although other studies report higher frequencies [15].

Severe manifestations (prostration, anemia, jaundice, convulsions, thrombocytopenia) are consistent with regional data [16–21].

The low mortality rate (1.97%) demonstrates effective management, but the dependence on quinine underlines the need for better availability of artesunate.

Conclusion

Severe malaria in children remains common at CHME, mainly affecting those under five years old.

It is mainly associated with prostration, anemia, altered consciousness and thrombocytopenia.

The overall trend is favorable, but requires:

- Early diagnosis.
- Continued availability of recommended injectable treatments.
- Strengthening prevention and awareness.

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